

Data Stewardship Competency Framework

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Adelaide

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The project undertaken by the University of Adelaide investigated the role of Data Steward as defined in the University of Adelaide Research Data and Primary Materials Policy. A working group, comprised of researchers, library staff and research infrastructure staff, have designed the Data Steward Competency Framework (DSCF) which outlines the research data management (RDM) needs for any research project in any discipline. The DSCF is flexible enough to be used by any university or institute and is able to be adapted for specific disciplines. The [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) element being tested is Support, Training and Guidance although the project also links with other areas of the framework including Culture Change, RDM Planning and also Policy. In line with the element we are testing, the aim of the project is to bring together a suite of training, information and resources that can be used by a data steward (researcher) to assist with RDM.

Resulting Improvements

The project has resulted in improved communications and a better understanding of financial and human resourcing limitations as they affect different stakeholders. This has led to further dialogue with researchers to understand their needs.

Next Steps

The work in this project will be ongoing with the DSCF being made available to researchers and communication throughout the University regarding RDM training and the role of the Data Steward continuing.

Project Outputs

The Data Steward Competency Framework (DSCF), University of Adelaide.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7033760>

[University of Adelaide full project report](#)

The DSCF can be used by other universities to adapt as they wish. Possible adaptations could include linking to university repositories, tools or policies or linking to external training.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).